

Availability and Utilization of Laboratory Facilities as Correlates of Performance in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Giwa Educational Zone, Kaduna State

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Abstract

The study investigated Correlation between availability and utilization of Laboratory facilities on performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational Zone, Kaduna State” The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class two (SS 2) Chemistry students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Giwa educational zone. A sample size of two hundred and sixty-two (262) respondents were randomly selected from the target population. Chemistry Student Questionnaires (CSQ), Chemistry teachers Questionnaires (CTQ) and School administrators Questionnaires (SAQ) were adopted and validated by experts. They were found to have reliability coefficient of 0.78, 0.80 and 0.85 respectively. Three research objectives, with corresponding research questions and hypotheses were raised and tested at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance. Data collected were analysed using Frequency and percentages and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). the result revealed that significant relationship exist between the availability of chemistry laboratory facilities, adequacy of chemistry laboratory facilities, level of utilization of chemistry laboratory facilities, chemistry teachers’ qualifications ,number of chemistry teachers and academic performance in Chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Education zone, Kaduna State. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the utilization of chemistry practical in senior secondary schools is faced with problems ranging from poor teaching personnel in terms of qualification and adequacy, poor level of priority given to practical work by chemistry teachers to the non-availability of space, equipment and apparatus for practical work. it was recommended among others that Chemistry laboratory facilities should be made available in all secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

Key words: Academic performance, Laboratory facilities, Chemistry

Introduction

Science education is the education that comprises the knowledge of sciences with the study of education. Olanrewaju (2018), sees science education as the study of all science subjects like Biology, Physics, Chemistry and others using variety methods of teaching so as to impact scientific knowledge to various learners. West African Examination Council’s (WAEC) syllabus (WAEC, 2012), suggested that all science subjects (Chemistry inclusive) in the schools should taught in such a way that practical would be given a special preference, because of the significance it has in the studies of sciences. According to Ababio (2019), Chemistry is the branch of science that studies the composition, properties and uses of matter. It studies how and why substances combine or separate to form other substances, and how various substances interact with energy. Yahaya et al. (2021) also define Chemistry as a science subject offered in Senior Secondary Schools in Nigeria as a core subject. To be given an admission to study courses like Medicine, pharmacy, Nursing, Engineering and many other physical science courses in university, credit in chemistry is required. Umahaba, Olajide & Lawal (2015) state that the developed countries forged ahead by understanding the relevance of Chemistry and its role in the national economy, in the study of medicine, pharmacy, medicine and other technologically based courses.

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One of the main objectives of teaching Chemistry in the Senior Secondary schools is for the students to gain basic theoretical and practical knowledge coupled with the skills that can be applied to meet the societal needs of creating employment and wealth. The skills will not only help students to find out, use and understand the scientific knowledge and technology of today but also tomorrow (FRN, 2012). This can only be achieved where there are well-equipped laboratories in the secondary schools. Chemistry laboratory is a building in a school set up and equipped with facilities meant for the conduction of scientific experiments. The chemistry laboratory contains facilities such as equipment, chemicals as well as gadgets used for effective performance of practical lessons. Ogunyemi and Adesoji (2000) observed that, without the use of laboratory facilities, some objectives of teaching chemistry practical may not be achieved such as; students' appreciation of scientific method of learning chemistry which has to do with experimentation, observation, recording, deduction and interpretation of scientific data accurately. Academic performance according to Shuaibu (2017) is the application of knowledge gained or skills developed in academic activity designed by test scores or marks assigned by the training instructor. According to WAEC Chief Examiner's report (2016, 2017, 2018, 2019), there were a series of poor performance in Chemistry practicals. Some of the suggestions made are: teachers and students have to work hard in the classrooms and laboratories, teachers should use their school laboratories very well, teachers must endeavor to expose candidates to a lot of practical exercises and teachers must make time to mark the exercises and draw the attention of students to essential points in recording tests, observation and inferences made. It was also suggested that additional practical equipment should be supplied to schools as the class size is increasing, more time should be allocated to practical to give students more chance to practice. This will enable them to relate theory with practical and also see its relevance in life.

Statement of the Research problem

Most schools in Nigeria are just claiming to teach chemistry at the secondary level without laboratory facilities, this clearly shows that no practical is taken place in such schools and where the laboratories exist, they are poorly equipped with the facilities (Ogunyeye, 2000). Inadequate resources for teaching and learning of Chemistry are common in secondary schools in Nigeria (Giwa Local Government of Kaduna State inclusive). And where little is provided is not sufficient to go round the students. Therefore, effective learning cannot be achieved (Bassey, 2002). Usman (2000) clarifies that the provision of resources (laboratory facilities) and their effective administration makes teaching easier and faster. This in turn encourages students to learn new ideas well and enhances their academic excellence. This study aims to identify the Effects of Laboratory Facilities on Senior Secondary Students' Academic Performance in Chemistry among Selected Secondary Schools in Giwa Local Government Area, Kaduna, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to;

1. Determine the relationship between availability of laboratory facilities and performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State
2. Determine the relationship between level of laboratory equipment and performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State
3. Determine the relationship between adequacy of laboratory facilities and performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State

Research questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the influence of availability of laboratory facilities on performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State?
2. What is the influence of laboratory equipment on performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State?
3. What is the influence of adequacy of laboratory facilities on performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance

1. **H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between availability of laboratory facilities and academic performance in chemistry among senior secondary school students in Giwa Education Zone

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2. **H₀₂:** There is no significance relationship between adequacy of laboratory facilities and academic performance in chemistry among senior secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone
3. **H₀₃:** There is no significant relationship in the level of utilization of laboratory facilities and academic performance in chemistry among senior secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone

Methodology

The research design was descriptive survey. The study investigated the availability of chemistry laboratories and laboratory equipment. It equally investigated the frequency of practical activities among secondary schools in Giwa local government. The population for the study comprised of all the 1750 SS 2 Chemistry Students and teachers in Giwa local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. A sample of 250 SS 2 chemistry students were randomly selected. Three instruments were adapted by the researchers and validated by experts are used to collect data for the study. The instruments were; Chemistry Student Questionnaires (CSQ), Chemistry teachers Questionnaires (CTQ) and School administrators Questionnaires (SAQ). Some items in the questionnaires were structured (closed ended), to measure the objective responses and others were unstructured (open ended) to measure the subjective responses. The Data was collected using fixed- and opened-response questionnaire, questionnaires were distributed at each school with the assistance of their chemistry teachers and were given to the chemistry students, chemistry teachers and school administrator to answer. The research hypotheses were tested using Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC) test at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level. A correlation of 0.9 was found on two successive administrations

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: What is the influence of availability of laboratory facilities on performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State?

Table 1: Respondents' opinion on the availability of Chemistry Laboratory Facilities for practical in Senior Secondary Schools in Giwa

STATEMENT	SA		A		D		SD	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Preparation room is available	103	56.3	30	16.4	34	18.6	16	8.7
Electricity supply is available	75	41	88	48.1	0	0	20	10.9
Water and heat supply are available	123	67.2	50	27.3	10	5.5	0	0
Chemicals/Reagents are available	78	33.9	30	15.4	20	12	92	38.7
Storage room and glass wares available	133	72.7	50	27.3	0	0	0	0
First aid kits are available	33	18	10	5.5	40	21.9	100	54.6
Fire extinguishers are available	90	49.2	50	27.3	25	13.7	18	9.8
Safety materials are available	10	5.5	35	19.1	18	6.5	120	69.8
Space for class work are available	130	71	23	12.6	15	8.2	15	8.2
Other consumable materials are available	43	23.5	10	5.5	70	38.3	60	32.7

Key: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree

Table 1 indicates respondents' opinions with regard to utilization of chemistry laboratory facility for practical in secondary schools in Giwa. 53 respondents (29%) agreed that preparation room are utilized. while, 130 respondents (71%) disagreed. It implies that preparation room are not utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area. 153 respondents (84.6%) agreed that electricity supply is well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical while 30 respondents (15.4%) disagreed. It means that electricity supply is well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area. 183 respondents (100%) agreed that water and heat supply is well utilized in chemistry laboratories. 138 respondents (75.4%) agreed that chemical/reagent are well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical while 50 respondents (23.6%) disagreed. It means that chemicals/reagents are well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical. 143 respondents (78.2%) agreed that Storage room and glass wares are well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical while 40 respondents (21.8%) disagreed. 43 respondents (23.5%) agreed that first aid kit are well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical. While 140 respondents (76.5%) disagreed. 53 respondents (29%) agreed that fire extinguisher are well utilized in chemistry laboratory. While 130 respondents (71%) disagreed. 53 respondents (29%) agreed that safety materials are well utilized in chemistry laboratory, while 130 respondents (71%) disagreed. 183 respondents (100%)

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agreed that space for class work are well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area. 33 respondents (18.1%) agreed that consumable materials are well utilized in chemistry laboratory. While 150 respondents (81.9%) disagreed. It implies that other consumable materials are not well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area

Research Question Two: What is the influence of laboratory equipment on performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State?

Table 2: Opinions of the Respondents on the adequacy of Chemistry Laboratory Facilities for practical in Senior Secondary Schools in Giwa

S/N	STATEMENT	SA		A		D		SD	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Preparation room are adequate	143	78.1	20	10.9	10	5.5	10	5.5
2	Electricity supply is adequate	103	56.3	20	10.9	55	30	5	2.7
3	Water and heat supply are adequate	50	28.3	30	16.4	40	20	98	35.3
4	Chemicals/ Reagents are adequate	18	8.3	30	18	68	30	88	48.7
5	Storage room and glass wares are adequate	123	67.2	20	10.9	30	16.4	10	5.5
6	First aid kits are adequate	50	27.3	80	43.7	23	12.6	30	16.4
7	Fire extinguishers are adequate	93	50.8	40	21.9	33	18	20	10.9
8	Safety material are adequate	43	23.5	20	10.9	25	13.7	75	40.9
9	Space for class work are adequate	135	73.8	28	15.3	15	8.2	5	2.7
10	Other consumable material are adequate	23	12.6	50	27.3	60	32.8	50	27.3

Table 2 showed the opinions of the respondents on the adequacy of Chemistry Laboratory Facilities for practical in senior secondary schools in Giwa. 163 respondents (89%) agreed that preparation room are adequate while 20 (11%) disagreed. 123 respondents (67.2%) agreed that electricity supply is adequate in chemistry laboratories. While 60 respondents (32.8%) disagreed. It indicates that electricity supply is adequate. 80 respondents (44.3%) agreed that water and heat supply is adequate while 55.7% disagree. 48 respondents (26%) agreed that Chemicals/reagents are adequate. While 156 respondents (73.7%) disagreed. It means that chemicals/reagents are not adequate. 143 respondents (78.1%) agreed that Storage room and glass wares are adequate chemistry laboratories. While 40 respondents (21.9%) disagreed. 130 respondents (71%) agreed that first aid kit are adequate. While 53 respondents (29%) disagreed. 133 respondents (72.7%) agreed that fire extinguishers are adequate. While 50 respondents (27.3%) percent disagreed. 83 respondents (45.4%) percent agreed that safety materials are adequate in chemistry laboratories. While 100 respondents (54%) disagreed. 163 respondents (89.1%) agreed that space for class work are adequate in chemistry laboratories. While 20 respondents (10.9%) disagreed. 73 respondents (39.9%) agreed that consumable materials are adequate in chemistry laboratories. While 110 respondents (60.1%) disagreed. It implies that other consumable materials adequate in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area.

Research Question Three: What is the influence of adequacy of laboratory facilities on performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State?

Table 3: Opinions of the Respondents upon the level of usage of Chemistry Laboratory equipment for practical in Giwa Secondary schools

S/N	STATEMENT	SA		A		D		SD	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Preparation room are utilized	43	23.5	10	5.5	50	27.3	80	43.7
2	Electricity supply is utilized	103	56.3	50	27.3	20	11	10	5.5
3	Water and heat supply is utilized	153	83.6	30	16.4	0	0	0	0
4	Chemicals /Reagents are utilized	113	61.7	25	13.7	40	21.9	10	5.5
5	Storage room and glass wares are utilized	120	65.6	23	12.6	15	8.2	25	13.7
6	First aid kits is utilized	28	15.3	15	8.2	70	38.3	70	38.3
7	Fire extinguisher are utilized	30	16.4	23	12.6	80	43.7	50	27.3
8	Safety materials are utilized	18	9.8	35	19.1	100	55.6	30	16.4

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9	Space for class work are utilized	133	72.7	50	27.3	0	0	0	0
10	Other consumable materials are utilized	10	5.5	23	12.6	80	55.6	70	38.3

Table 3 pointed out the opinions of the respondents on the utilization Chemistry Laboratory Facility for practical in secondary schools in Giwa. 53 respondents (29%) agreed that preparation room are utilized in chemistry laboratories for practical. while 130 respondents (71%) disagreed. 153 respondents (84.6%) agreed electricity supply is well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical. While 30 respondents (15.4%) percent disagreed. 183 respondents (100%) agreed that water and heat supply is well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area. 138 respondents (75.4%) agreed that chemical/reagent are well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical. While 50 respondents (23.6%) disagreed. 143 respondents (78.2%) agreed that Storage room and glass wares are well utilized. While 40 respondents (21.8%) disagreed. 43 respondents (23.5%) agreed that first aid kit are well utilized. While 140 respondents (76.5%) disagreed. 53 respondents (29%) agreed that fire extinguishers are well utilized. While 130 respondents (71%) disagreed. 53 respondents (29%) agreed that safety materials are well utilized. While 130 respondents (71%) percent disagreed. 183 respondents (100%) percent agreed that space for class work are well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area. 33 respondents (18.1%) percent agreed that consumable materials are well utilized. While 150 respondents (81.9%) disagreed. It implies that other consumable materials are not well utilized in chemistry laboratory for practical in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area.

Hypotheses testing

The formulated hypotheses tested at significant level of $P \leq 0.05$

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between availability of laboratory facilities and academic performance in chemistry among senior secondary school students in Giwa Education Zone

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship Between Availability of Laboratory Facilities and Students' Academic Performance.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	1	2
Academic Performance	253	32.100	11.446	1.000	
Availability	010	12.200	10.838	.984**	1.000

**Correlation is at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level (2-tailed).

Table 4 revealed that a significant relationship exists between availability of chemistry laboratory facilities for practical and students' academic performance in Giwa Local Government area ($r = 0.984$, $P < 0.05$). This shows that availability of chemistry laboratory facilities for practical has relationship with students' academic performance. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significance relationship between availability of chemistry laboratory facilities for practical and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Giwa.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significance relationship between adequacy of laboratory facilities and academic performance in chemistry among senior secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone

Table 5: Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing the relation between the adequacy of chemistry laboratory equipment and students' performance among secondary students in Giwa.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	1	2
Academic Performance	253	32.100	11.446	1.000	
Adequacy	010	28.300	10.174	.855**	1.000

**Correlation is significant at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level (2-tailed).

Table 5 above revealed that a significant relationship exists between adequacy of chemistry laboratory facilities for practical and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area ($r = 0.855$, $P < 0.05$). This shows that adequacy of chemistry laboratory facilities have relationship with the academic performance of secondary school students in Giwa Local Government Area. Therefore, the hypothesis two is hereby rejected.

Hypotheses Three: There is no significant relationship in the level of utilization of laboratory facilities and academic performance in chemistry among senior secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone

Table 6: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between level of Utilization of Chemistry Laboratory facilities and Students' Academic Performance

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Variables	N	Mean	SD	1	2
Academic Performance	253	32.100	11.446	1.000	
Utilization	010	7.400	8.479	.959**	1.000

**Correlation is significant at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level (2-tailed).

Table 6 above revealed that a significant relationship exists between level of utilization of chemistry laboratory facilities in senior secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area and students' academic performance ($r = 0.959$, $P < 0.05$). This shows that the level of utilization of chemistry laboratory facilities in secondary schools have relationship with students' academic performance in Giwa Local Government Area. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of the findings

The result from Table 4 revealed the correlation of the availability of chemistry laboratory facilities and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State. This is in agreement with Lunetta (2007) who had it that laboratory facilities have the potential to enhance cognitive growth in students. Table 5 showed that the adequacy of chemistry laboratory facilities is significantly related to the students' academic performance in secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The nature of curriculum content, emphasizing theoretical knowledge, inadequate periods for chemistry and chemistry practical, inadequate facilities and equipment, reagent, support staff for laboratories, funding improvisation of materials, teachers' knowledge of practical, teachers' qualification, separate laboratories for chemistry, textbooks, work books and manuals for practical chemistry all constitute constraints toward effective utilization. These findings confirm the submission of Ogunleye (2002) and Olayiwola (1999) on the poor state of implementation, as it relates to facilities required for the effective implementation of practical work in chemistry. In hypothesis III, the result of the test showed that the frequency of usage of chemistry laboratory facilities is significantly related with students' academic performance. This finding is in line with the findings of Margil (2009) who find out that drill and practice help learners to understand and pass practical examination in school.

Conclusion

From the results and implications of findings it was concluded that:

The utilization of chemistry practical in senior secondary schools is still faced with problems ranging from poor teaching personnel in terms of qualification and adequacy, poor level of priority given to practical work by chemistry teachers to the non-availability of space, equipment and apparatus for practical work.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made;

1. There should be provision of adequate laboratory facilities all Senior Secondary Schools in Giwa Local Government.
2. The school heads should ensure that the teachers utilized all the chemistry laboratory facilities for effective teaching and learning in senior secondary schools in Giwa Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

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